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EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE: A THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract: The study examined the impact of human resource development on employees' performance from a theoretical perspective. The employee performance components identified are ability to meet deadlines, quality of work, teamwork, and problem solving. While the dimensions of human resource development identified are mentoring, training, performance appraisal, and compensation/benefits. The study notes that a well-coordinated and implemented HRD practices results to improved organizations productivity and individual employees' performance. The study also notes that implementation of human resource development leads to improved organizational efficiency and development of innovative competitive advantages for organizations. The study concluded that human resource development programmes serves as a critical organizational strategy for improving employees' effectiveness, productivity, satisfaction, motivation, and innovation at work. In addition, the implementation of effective human resources development programs helps to create the workforce competency that enables the organization to function efficiently. It is recommended that managements should make human resource development a serious aspect of their overall organizational strategy, and also support all activities put in place to develop the employees in order to ensure that employees develop the necessary competencies and capacity needed to drive organizational performance and survival. Furthermore, organizations should constantly train and retrain their employees and management to develop vital conceptual, technical and interpersonal competences that is vital for high positive outcomes in organizations. Organizations should devise effective plans in investing in the various aspect of human capital as this does not only help them to attain greater performance but achieve long-term survival.

Keywords: Human Resource Development, Employees' Performance, Problem Solving, Competitive Advantage

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Introduction

Today, several business organizations are investing in their human resources as a strategy to improve organizational effectiveness, and to boost their competitiveness (Kareem and Hussein, 2019), in order to gain long-term competitive advantage in the market arena. To do this, organizations are utilizing systematic approaches designed to enhance individual and group competencies through practices for career development, organizational growth, and training and development. According to Afroz (2018), human resource development consists of a variety of performance-based learning activities that are both organized and unstructured and that enhance both individual and organizational competencies in order to meet changes in the business environment.

Agwu and Ogiriki (2014) contend that the relationship between human resource development and human resource management promotes organizational learning and enhances human resource orientation, which in turn improves employee performance and boosts organizational performance. According to Aidah (2013), the fundamental principle of human resource development (HRD) is to improve organizational performance through increasing employee engagement as well as knowledge, skills, and capacities. According to Asfaw, Argaw, and Bayissa (2015), the fundamental goal of HRD is to enhance and develop employee skills in order to help organizations get the most out of their human resources. To create the workforce competency that enables the organization to function efficiently, businesses must use a variety of human resource development techniques (ALDamore, Yazam, & Ahmid, 2021). Ananthalakshmi and Ming (2019) stress that firms should place more of an emphasis on HRD methods including training and development, employee participation, and organizational development if they want to attain superior performance.

The effect of human resource development on employee performance has been the subject of numerous researches. However, a critical examination of these publications reveals that the majority of them were produced in advanced Asian, European, and American nations, where corporate management techniques and culture are far different from those in Nigeria. According to Katou (2009), there is still a void in the empirical study on HRD; there is no definite model to look at how HRD practices might raise employee performance. The relationship between HRD practices and employee performance has only been the subject of a small number of empirical studies (Hassan & Mohammed, 2016). There aren't many studies or researches that have focused on how HRD techniques affect employee performance, especially in Nigeria. In few articles that have been done, employee performance was handled as one variable. We proposed a wellconceived framework to examine how HRD constructs (mentoring, training, performance appraisal, and compensation) can enhance employee performance constructs (ability to meet deadlines, quality of work, teamwork, and problem-solving) on an individual basis in response to this gap in the literature. Based on this, this study seeks to theoretical examine the impact of HRD on employee performance.

Literature Review

Concept of Human Resource Development

The idea that a company's human resources and human capital are sources of competitive advantage was hardly acknowledged until recently. Without controlling performance and simultaneously enhancing employee ability and competence, competitiveness cannot be attained. The most substantial contribution to individual and organizational learning, as well as to increasing organizational efficiency and fostering growth, may come through performance management (Adhikari, 2010). The employment landscape has drastically changed, technology is

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having an impact on behaviors and interactions, and societies are becoming more multicultural and global. Employability is increasingly a top priority for businesses as the level of globalization develops.

Employers today want non-technical talents in addition to technical skills from their employees (Mansour & Jason, 2016). Therefore, the HRD role is distinct from HRM and personnel functions.

Therefore, for the purposes of this study, we define HRD as a systematic process of creating strategic human resources (mentoring, training, performance appraisal, and compensation) in order to help the organization achieve its strategic goals, including improving employees' ability to meet deadlines, produce high-quality work, work reliably as a team, and problem solving.

Dimensions of Human Resource Development

Mentoring

Mentoring is one of the few instruments available for developing tomorrow's competent workers. It is also utilized to maintain an organization's competitive advantage by enhancing organizational capacities and intelligence (Adeyemi, 2013). Both public and private organizations have two distinct resources: people and things. Without the former, the latter is useless. The former is people, workforce, manpower, or employee of such businesses. According to Okurame and Balogun (2013), mentoring refers to the practices frequently planned and supported by management to help employees grow and sustain the organization's competitive advantage. Yahya, Tan, and Tay (2017) stated that organizations are social systems where human resources are the most significant variables for effectiveness and efficiency as a result of the interest in mentoring. Organizations cannot prosper without the efforts of their workers and greater performance. They need effective managers and employees to attain their goals.

Training

For some businesses, training has become the Holy Grail, a sign of how much the management genuinely cares about its employees (Hamid, 2011). Hamid (2011) continued by stating that a significant factor in determining how well an organization performs is the efficiency with which it manages, develops, motivates, involves, and engages the willing contribution of individuals who work there. In light of this, Mondy, Noe, and Premeaux (2002) define training as all activities intended to give learners the information and skills necessary for carrying out their current occupations. It is an organizational initiative designed to aid a worker in acquiring the fundamental knowledge needed for the effective performance of the tasks and duties for which he was employed. It encompasses all actions taken to expose a worker to increased responsibilities and important leadership roles within an organization's hierarchical structure. It is the comprehensive process by which a person's behavior is changed to fit a predetermined and specific pattern, involving those activities that primarily aim to provide the skills, knowledge, and attitude necessary for a group or related occupation or function in any field of occupation (Zigon, 2002; Aderinto, 1986; Ruhert, 1992).

Performance Appraisal

Numerous authors have provided numerous definitions of performance evaluation. According to Cook and Crossman (2018), performance evaluation is the process of evaluating and documenting employee performance with the goal of making judgments regarding the employee. It is described by Gabris and Ihrke (2017) as a formal and structured interaction between a subordinate and supervisor that typically takes the form of a periodic interview. During this interview, the subordinate's work performance is reviewed and discussed with the goal of

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identifying areas for improvement and skill development, as well as opportunities for promotion and transfer to new job tasks and positions within the organization (Eldman, 2017).

According to North (2002), a performance appraisal is a planned, formal conversation between a subordinate and supervisor that typically takes the form of a regular interview. During this conversation, the subordinate's work performance is examined and discussed in order to pinpoint any areas for improvement and skill development. In other words, performance assessment is a formal system of monitoring, analyzing, and influencing an employee's job-related characteristics, actions, and results in order to assess an employee's productivity and evaluate whether it can be increased (Konobear, 2002)

Compensation

Offering employees financial value in exchange for the effort they put forth in completing their tasks is known as compensation. According to Sherman and Snell (1998), employee benefits and remuneration include all forms of pay, cash bonuses, commissions, leaves, recognition programs, flexible work schedules, and health insurance. Any type of monetary return, including intangible services and advantages provided to a person, is another way to define compensation (Milkovich & Newman, 1999). According to Bergmann and Scarpello (2001), the pay scheme is helpful in boosting promoter output toward the achievement of the company's objectives. In addition, paying employees is seen to be the biggest expense in running a corporation. In a similar line, remuneration systems serve as tools for increasing employee motivation and job performance.

Concept of Employees' Performance

The utilization of knowledge, skills, experiences, and talents by employees to complete the duties assigned to them and requested by their supervisors is referred to as performance. The value of an employee's performance can help with making the best decisions, surviving and succeeding in different organizations, assessing and achieving performance goals, increasing efficiency, and considering the cost of the resources used to measure the quantity and quality of work completed. A key component in achieving stated goals is employee performance. It usually depends on how well an employee performs their job obligations and on how well they behave. As a result, the organization must establish precise, quantifiable criteria and use them all in concert as a guide. General observations has showed that employee productivity is measured by the quality and quantity of work completed in the course of fulfilling their varied tasks.

As a result, an employee's performance is typically measured by how well they are able to achieve a foreseeable objective or accomplish a task with the expected level of quality (Farah and Sproull, 2000). Numerous elements regarding employee performance were found in studies. Each member's devotion to their duty is included (Senior, 1997). Mesmer-Magnus & DeChurch (2009) discussed the cohesiveness of the team, the effectiveness of the information-sharing process, the members' alignment with the team's objectives, and the level of agreement among them about goalsetting strategies (Plowman and McDonough 2010). The idea that effective information-sharing among workers promotes performance and profitability through interaction is substantially supported by employee performance based on the influence of HRD (Mesmer-Magnus, Asencio, Seely, & DeChurch, 2015). The emotional intelligence of the team members also affects employee performance (Rapisarda,2002). Individuals with consistent and pleasant emotional intelligence would be good to team cohesion and performance, according to research by Davies, Stankov, and Roberts (1998). The five criteria for measuring employee

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performance, according to Mathis and Jackson (2012), are quantity, quality, punctuality, attendance, and ability to cooperate.

Measures of Employee Performance

Ability to Meet Deadlines: The phrase "ability to meet deadlines" refers to an organization's capacity to keep to deadlines. In this perspective, an individual or organization does their utmost to ensure that the needs of consumers and clients are addressed in the most satisfactory way possible, taking into account quantity, quality, and timing.

The term "time management" refers to a process made up of a number of processes, including the analysis of our time habits, the explanation of our goals, the setting of our priorities, the planning of effective outcomes, and the adoption of proactive measures against time wasters. Nothing but a problem, time management is essential to work performance. Time is the most valuable and limited resource that cannot be replaced after it has been used, so managers and employees alike must take the necessary precautions to prevent time loss. (Gupta 2001). Being efficient in life requires learning to manage time, which is a concept that is uniquely personal. This is easier said than done for many of us since our methods are determined by our presumptions about the nature of our professions and the circumstances in our environment. Therefore, the power to set time, plan time, and govern time is personal. A person's capacity for effective time management will enable him or her to arrange his activities, carry them out within the allocated timeframe, and manage his or her time in accordance with schedules in order to fulfill deadlines for any given job activity.

Quality of Work: Work that meets and goes above client or corporate expectations is referred to as being of high quality. You must apply your skills to your task at the highest level in order to conduct quality work. It can be difficult to define quality because it depends on the particular clients or employers. Quality work typically complies with all timeline criteria, exceeds completion standards, and offers correct information. Quality always wins out over quantity, especially when taking into account worker productivity. Meeting deadlines is crucial and affects each employee's performance, however if the final product is subpar, meeting deadlines become less relevant. Ideally, you want workers who complete tasks accurately the first time. It is difficult to evaluate someone's work on a consistent basis. The exact activities and responsibilities of the employee, as well as the industry you are in, strongly influence what and how you measure. The percentage of work output that is rejected or needs to be redone is one item to take into account, though. With the use of talent management software, you can see the progress of new hires' onboarding, current employees' 360-degree performance reviews, and more to acquire a deeper understanding of each person's performance.

Teamwork: Teamwork, according to Richard (1991), is the accomplishment of a certain objective by two or more people sharing tasks and responsibilities. Employee collaboration to accomplish a shared goal while keeping in mind the interests of the entire group rather than individual interests was the focus of earlier research on teamwork (Chukwudi, 2014). Cook et al. (1998) noted that while many scholars agree that organizations can accomplish their aims or objectives through individuals, their main success still lies in the objectives accomplished by teams (teamwork). Teamwork is a collaborative endeavor in which each member contributes their own ideas and efforts to the success of the entire group. The aforementioned claim does not imply that people are any less significant to businesses, but it does imply that successful teamwork is necessary for

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individual accomplishments (Nicholas and Reenen, 2007). Employees are better able to work together, develop their skills, and provide helpful responses when they are working as a team (Jones et al., 2007).

Reliability and Problem Solving: A system or component's reliability refers to its capacity to carry out its intended function under predetermined circumstances repeatedly without experiencing a malfunction. A trustworthy product has a good chance of consistently performing as promised. How frequently a product fails and how long it lasts before failing can both be used to gauge how reliable it is. To put it another way, a dependable product never fails. It operates predictably and consistently.

In order to discover answers for the problems that arise in daily life, humans use a certain set of abilities as well as cognitive, affective, and behavioral processes (Paul and Charles, 1997). The relationship between problem-solving, psychological adjustment, and mental health has been the subject of numerous studies. Paul, et al (2004) note that problem-solving skills have been connected to symptoms of physical health as well as stress, depression, and maladaptive behavior. As a result, many clinicians who specialize in behavior therapy and work to empower people in order to improve their well-being and raise their life satisfaction appear to find problem-solving abilities to be highly helpful. It can also be a helpful tool for many professionals, such as educators, who can use it to better their own socio-emotional and personal well-being as well as the training and psychosocial development of their students.

Mentoring and Employee Performance

Amanda and Akpana (2023) assert that mentorship programs play an important role in employee performance and are enhanced through knowledge transfer and career development. They recommended that organizations should create the atmosphere that encourages mentoring for the workers in the organization so as to ensure organizational longevity and employee productivity. Odunayo (2022) found that through apprenticeship training, employees are able to improve their productivity. In addition, it found that coaching had a significant influence on employee commitment. It further found that through employee orientation, the employees are able to improve their citizenship behaviour in the organization.

Nyengidiki and Nyengidiki (2020) found a positive significant relationship between mentoring and employee performance improvement in public hospitals in Rivers State. The study concluded that mentoring significantly predicted employee performance improvement in public hospitals in Rivers State.

Training and Employee Performance

Training acts as a catalyst that spurs employees to several organizational positive behaviors/actions. According to Kaumi, Yakaka and Adda (2023) modern organizations have realized the importance of training in employees' development, and have begun to use on-job training as a tool for increasing employee satisfaction. Lola, Afrizal, Meri and Ira (2023) note that, training provide a positive significant influence on the performance of employees of the South Padang Sub-District Office; Work ability has a positive influence on the Performance of South Padang District Office Employees; organizational commitment has a negative influence on the performance of employees of the Padang Selatan sub-district office; training, employability and organizational commitment jointly have a positive effect on the performance of employees of the South Padang District Office.

Ashigar, Yakaka and Adda (2023) found training and development to be crucial tool for increasing employee performance as well as their effectiveness, productivity, satisfaction, motivation, and innovation at work. Finding

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the correct learning opportunities for employees will aid the firm in reaching its competitive posture in the contemporary global marketplace.

Performance Appraisal and Employee Performance

Arimie and Orobosa (2023) observed that performance appraisal does not only promote organizational performance but provides potency in determining employee capacity, skills acquisition, and experience for career advancement. Rodrigues, Gomes and Junça-Silva (2023) revealed that private sector employees showed higher levels of satisfaction with their performance appraisal than those from the public sector. Furthermore, the results indicated that the usefulness and accuracy of the performance appraisal had a significant and positive relationship with employees' satisfaction with their last performance appraisal, and this relationship was partially mediated by satisfaction with the performance appraisal, both in the public and private sectors. Achamyelah, Cherinet, Minwyelet and Lemessa (2023) indicated that the independent variables for the organization policy, effective leadership, employee benefit, performance appraisal, workplace interaction, and work-life balance have a positive relationship with employee productivity.

Compensation/Benefits and Employee Performance

Alliu and Babatunde (2023) reveals that employee compensation management has a positive significant effect on profitability, indicating that profitability is a determining factor in employee compensation management. It was concluded that compensation management is important to organizational performance through profitability. Fulmer, Gerhart and Kim (2023) show that employee compensation continues to be an under-studied topic despite its clear importance to employees' lives and its economic significance for organizations and society. The proportion of academic research on compensation in comparison with other HR topics has been lower than the relative proportion of interest in compensation expressed in HR practitioner journals.

Okwudili and Edeh (2017) revealed that direct compensation is positively associated with employee performance. Secondly, indirect compensation was found to significantly associate with employee performance. The study concludes that civil service should see compensation as a tool that will enhance employee performance. It was recommended that civil service commission should employ qualified human resource personnel that will oversee the affairs of employee compensation as this will remove the bottleneck surrounding the non-implementation of employees' compensation.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The positive effect of human resources development in organizations can never be over emphasized. Organizations that fail to develop its human resource component is indirectly preparing serious disaster. Human resource development thus, is a critical organizational strategy for improving employees' effectiveness, productivity, satisfaction, motivation, and innovation at work. In addition, the implementation of effective human resources development programs helps to create the workforce competency that enables the organization to function efficiently. It is recommended that managements should make human resource development a serious aspect of their overall organizational strategy, and also support all activities put in place to develop the employees in order to ensure that employees develop the necessary competencies and capacity needed to drive organizational performance and survival. Moreover, Furthermore, organizations should constantly train and retrain their employees and management to develop vital conceptual, technical and interpersonal competences that is vital for high positive outcomes in organizations. Organizations should devise effective plans in investing in the various

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aspect of human capital as this does not only help them to attain greater performance but achieve long-term survival.

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